

The origin of the ancient Egyptian *ankh* symbol

A composition of the most
characteristic life symbols of ancient Egypt?

21 December 2023 Enno Neeteson

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10417569

Abstract

The etymology of the ankh symbol is still under debate, as there is no convincing evidence for the proposed source(s). This article addresses another possible source that may have served as a representation of the ancient Egyptian *ankh* symbol. This *ankh* symbol represents “life” so one would expect the source(s) to resemble this aspect. In early ancient Egypt, main aspects related to life were the Nile, the moment of sunrise and the (eastern) horizon. The Nile as the source for agriculture, the rising sun in the eastern horizon as the reborn god Horus in the aspect of Horemakhet who restores order, and the life giving light of the sun. These three aspects somehow reflect the three consonants *‘nh* that define the *ankh* symbol. The development of the ankh symbol occurred at a time when the king's position and identity as the more violent Horus was under pressure, a more powerful but also friendlier identity was required. A link with the sun was obvious because it is the most powerful celestial object. Could it be that this ankh symbol has its origin in the image of the rising sun on the horizon shining its first rays on the waters of the Nile, which at the end of the First Dynasty was seen as the reborn Horus adding his life force to the Nile?

Introduction

One of the most fascinating symbols of ancient Egypt is probably the *ankh* symbol. The symbol represented life for the ancient Egyptians and although it first appeared approximately 5000 years ago, it still is a favorite symbol in use today. It probably owes its popularity to its resemblance to a human figure and it is believed to be the origin of the Christian cross. Already from the beginning of Egypt is “each hieroglyph a picture of a real thing that existed in the world of the ancient Egyptians” (Allen, 2002, 2). The question is which real thing was used for the *ankh* symbol and what was the motive to introduce such a symbol?

In the past there have been several studies on the etymology of the *ankh* symbol. The proposed origins are the waist-cord, knot, sandal strap, mirror, penis sheath or loincloth.¹ However, there is no convincing consensus yet on this subject. Probably the most fascinating thing about the *ankh* symbol is that to this day it is not clear what object it originally represented.

In this updated version I corrected some text, added new material and an epilogue.

Etymology

The *ankh* ideogram is a trilateral phonogram and consists of the three consonants ^c*nh*.² The hieroglyph for the consonant ^c is an upholding arm (still not clear what this represents). The *ankh* symbol means “life” but can also mean “sandal strap” or “mirror.”³ Often in texts the symbols can be seen together,

meaning the verb “to live”⁴ , as if to emphasize the relation of the two signs with these objects. Did the ancient Egyptians in the Early Dynastic Period (ca. 3150-2686 BCE) create words that were dominated by a preference for pronunciation or was the phonetic the result of primarily the choice of objects? It is known that especially in

the early dynastic period the ancient Egyptians liked to use those phonetic symbols that were as close as possible to the referring object.

Earliest appearance

One of the oldest evidences of an *ankh* symbol is a stone vessel [fig.1] shaped as an *ankh-ka* and dates to the First Dynasty (ca. 2900 BCE), currently on display in the MET museum in New York.⁵ This stone vessel clearly had a religious function.⁶ Another one of the earliest depictions of the *ankh* symbol dates from an ivory comb showing the Horus name of king Djet of the First Dynasty [fig.2] and on display in the Egyptian Museum Cairo.⁷ Also a piece of a bowl made of quartz and found in the tomb of king Den, on display in the Pennsylvania University Museum, shows an exact same ankh sign as on the ivory comb.⁸ There is an object in the Ashmolean Museum⁹ in Oxford dating from the period of first Dynasty king Narmer which shows very unclear images. In drawings copied from this object an ankh sign is shown, but to me the image on the original object is too vague to identify this as an ankh sign.

Figure 1. Libation Dish Depicting Ka-Arms Presenting an Ankh-Sign. Photo from MET museum.

Figure 2. Drawing of the ivory comb of king Djet with the earliest known depiction of an ankh sign.

King Den succeeded king Djet after an interim period during which probably Den's mother Meretneith was regent.¹⁰ Den is considered the most important ruler during the period of the first three dynasties.¹¹ His reign is characterized by the many innovations in almost every field, such as politics, economics, religion, and for this article the most important, the innovation in (written) language.¹² It was probably during his reign that more symbols related to life, such as the *shen* were introduced¹³, both symbols closely related to the *ankh* symbol. Abstract symbolism was further developed, a period in which subjects like "life", "heaven" and "eternity" were defined. Also on two stone vessels with Den's Horus name show the earliest evidence for a cult of the king's *ka*, related to our definition of the soul.¹⁴ The comb [fig.2] also shows the earliest surviving depiction of the heavens symbolized by the outspread wings of a falcon, another indication of the development of abstract symbolism in the language. And this may be "the oldest evidence for a link between the sun god and the king" (Cervello-Autuori, 2011, 1133), an indication that the solar cult was probably already under development during Den's reign. After king Den the use of the *ankh* symbol seems to disappear, but approximately a hundred years later it reappears during the reign of king Ninetjer of the Second Dynasty.¹⁵ The first clear standardized depictions of the *ankh* symbol we see during the Third Dynasty.¹⁶

The period when the *ankh* symbol first appears is during an innovative period in ancient Egypt. This is not surprising, as it coincides with a period of favorable floodings of the Nile. During the more than three thousand years of ancient Egyptian civilization, we can see that cultural flourishing and prosperity generally coincide with favorable floods of the Nile. The reverse is also true, a decline in prosperity can be observed during periods of unfavorable flooding of the Nile. It is likely that the hundred years of disappearance of the *ankh* symbol was related to the low Nile floods during the Second Dynasty that caused a decline in economic and cultural prosperity.¹⁷

The importance of the *ankh* symbol is unquestionable considering its prominent appearance on the walls of temples and in tombs of later dynasties. Only gods and later also the pharaoh (but only on special occasions) are shown holding the symbol of life.¹⁸ Not even the highest official was allowed to picture himself holding the *ankh* symbol at least till the Middle Kingdom.¹⁹

Ancient Egyptian view on life related sources

The *ankh* symbol represents life, but what defined life for the ancient Egyptians? Of course, the first thing that comes to mind is the Nile. There is no book on ancient Egypt or it begins with the famous words of Herodotus that Egypt is “a gift of the Nile.”²⁰ No life in Egypt without the Nile. The more surprising that there is no specific dedicated hieroglyph for the Nile. The Nile in ancient Egyptian texts is simply named *jtwr* “river.”

The second aspect that comes to mind when we look specifically at the ancient Egyptian culture is probably maintaining order. Chaos destroys life, maintaining order defeats chaos. No culture was so obsessed with maintaining order as the ancient Egyptians. The goddess Ma'at, often represented by a feather in ancient Egypt, embodied the principles of order and justice.²¹ However, rather than an active participant, she was more of a prescriptive force. She prescribed what was necessary to maintain order, but did not engage in active participation to defeat chaos. Ma'at was not worshipped nor had temples or shrines dedicated to her.²² A second Dynasty king named Sekhemib-peren-maat is the earliest reference to Ma'at presenting the king's role of maintaining order, although this role is generally seen from the Old Kingdom onwards.²³ The passive aspect can be seen in the “weighing of the heart” ritual described in the Book of the Dead, where the heart of the deceased is being weighed against Ma'at. Here the feather is the weight.

The duty of the king was to be the active aspect in maintaining the order with the principles of Ma'at as guidance or reference. In fact he executed these principles. The god Seth was the cause of chaos, and the only deity capable of defeating Seth was Horus. The victory of Horus ensured the restoration of order

based on the principles of Ma'at. Horus defeats the chaos of the night on the moment of sunrise. On this specific moment he was represented as Horemakhet, meaning Horus in the *akhet*. *Akhet* was the ancient Egyptian concept of the horizon, especially the eastern and western part of the horizon, the place where the celestial objects rise or set. At his accession to the throne, the king became Horus on earth so he could defeat the chaos on earth. This role of the king remained his main duty till the end of pharaonic rulership.

The third important aspect when we look at the concept of life in Ancient Egypt is obtaining eternal life through (re)birth. Another collective obsession of the ancient Egyptians when we look at their effort to obtain this eternal life. The mummification, the huge number of tombs and the complexity of their religious rituals demonstrate this. So what represented (re)birth in Ancient Egypt? Immediately we think of Osiris, the (farmers) fertility god, but perhaps at least as important is the place of (re)birth, the eastern horizon. At the eastern horizon, the sun is reborn every day. The rising of the sun on the horizon at dawn “makes all life possible” (Allan, 2002, 44). Besides, the cult of Osiris was not yet in place during the first four dynasties.²⁴ Fertility of course should be considered as one of the main aspects, however this would not be unique to the ancient Egyptians, for it is one of the universal aspects of life for all cultures around the world.

Other aspects could be considered part of the representation of life in the eyes of an ancient Egyptian, but the three just mentioned make up the top three especially in the early dynasties. If one or more objects for a symbol or hieroglyph was to represent life for the ancient Egyptians, it is expected to somehow be one or a combination of these three actors: the Nile, the (rising) sun, and the (eastern) horizon. Another reason for this choice of a top three is that the *ankh* symbol is a three-character symbol so it could have represented a combination of three objects.

An odd picture

For another study I was reading a work of Paul Moulin²⁵ where I saw a beautiful photograph taken of a rising sun reflecting its rays on the surface of a river. Immediately I saw the picture resembles somehow the *ankh* symbol. The balloon shaped sun looks like the upper part of the *ankh* sign, the horizontal bar is the horizon and the vertical leg is the reflection of the sun on the water. This photo was actually what motivated me to start this article. The sun in figure [3] looks like a balloon because of what is called a mirage effect.²⁶

Figure 3. Setting sun with a mirage effect. Photograph by Paul Moulin

A mirage of the sun is caused by a combination of factors. The one in the photo is called an inferior mirage. Hot air above a surface and cool air below causes light to be deflected. A situation not rare in Egypt with the hot desert land and the cool Nile water. Inferior mirages are the most common in deserts and another common mirage is the fata morgana. Those mirages usually take place just above the horizon. Many examples of mirages can be found on the internet showing pictures of such a balloon shaped sun. Inferior mirages must have occurred close to the Nile, especially during the period of flooding in the Delta region when the water surface extended over a larger area. “Since the Nile flowed around the city (Memphis) and covered it at the time of inundation” wrote the Roman historian Diodorus of Sicily around 50 BCE.²⁷ Memphis was the main capital

during the First Dynasty and was located on the west bank of the Nile near Saqqara. From this place, inhabitants could have observed mirages in the morning with the rising of the sun. Looking at the *ankh* symbol on the ivory comb of king Djed, it resembles most this inferior mirage.

The ancient Egyptians who saw this oddly shaped sun would certainly have given it special attention and significance.²⁸ When we, in our time, witness such a phenomenon it still touches us although we know that it is just a mirage, the refraction of light in an air layer. Imagine how the ancient Egyptians would have experienced such phenomenon without this scientific knowledge. It would have touched them deeply, especially since it is one of the very few moments in a day when you can safely look at the sun with your bare eyes and come face to face with the sun god. Since the construction of the Aswan Dam in the 20th century which prevented the flooding and consider the increase in smog from traffic, the mirage effect can probably no longer be seen today in the Delta region.

Chaos defeated

As mentioned above, the ancient Egyptians placed great importance to order, but this order could be disrupted by the god Seth. According to the ancient Egyptian mythology the god Horus was the only one powerful enough to defeat Seth. Sunrise was the moment of rebirth of Horus, called Horemakhet or “Horus in the Horizon” or “Horus of the East.”²⁹ After all, with sunrise the darkness of the night disappears. With the rising of the god Horus, Seth was defeated and the order restored. From the Fifth Dynasty onward, “Horus in the Horizon” personified with the sun god Ra became Ra-Horakhty.³⁰ The balloon shaped sun as in figure [3] marks this moment of the reborn Horus who has defeated Seth. We saw that the king was the personification of this Horus and his duty was to maintain this order in Egypt. That’s why only the king (and gods) could hold the ankh sign.

(Re)birth

The horizon played an important role in the religion of the ancient Egyptians. It was the place where the (re)birth of their celestial gods took place (only for the ones who set and rise on the horizon). The horizon was named the *akhet*, the “place of becoming.”³¹ The horizontal bar in the *ankh* symbol could represent the horizon as it is the “home of light.”³²

The third consonant of the *ankh* hieroglyph is *ḥ* represented by ☉. It is still not clear what it actually represents. According to Allen³³, it could represent a placenta. Is the placenta not directly related to birth and in this case to the just reborn sun god? Sometimes when just above the horizon, the sun appears to have horizontal stripes, which is also a mirage effect. Like the balloon shaped sun, this striped sun on the moment of sunrise must have had significant meaning for the ancient Egyptians as it is an odd appearance of their prime god.

Several *ankh* objects like amulets dating from the New Kingdom, were found showing the scarab with the sun and lotus flowers, symbols of the (re)birth of the sun god Ra. An example is an *ankh* shaped box, found in Tutankhamun’s tomb, showing a winged scarab on a lotus flower in the loop of the *ankh*. Obviously referring to (re)birth of the sun since the scarab was associated with the early morning sun named Khepri. This association of the ankh symbol with the sun god dates at least to the 5th dynasty but as we saw could be earlier.³⁴

Light giving life

Many temples in ancient Egypt were aligned in such a manner that the first rays of the rising sun were caught in the holy of holies where a statue of a god stood. This statue then became animated by these rays of light. Light was considered as part of the god, the life giving force named *ka*.³⁵ We all can feel the warmth of sunlight shining on our body and we know it comes from the sun. It is not strange to consider this aspect of the sun as a force? There is a parallel with the sun shining on the Nile. How would the ancient Egyptians interpret light reflections like this which shows that the warmth of the sun light touches the Nile?

Perhaps as if the *ka* of Horus was placed on the Nile to animate the Nile with its life force. This idea of a relationship between reflections of sunlight on water with divine beliefs is not new. And “Reflections of celestial events in water have often been undervalued in skyscape archaeology research.” (Cristofaro, 2020).

We saw that the consonant *n* in *ankh* is written in hieroglyph as , representing water. Although the Nile itself has no specific hieroglyph, which is rather surprising since it plays such an important role for the Egyptians, it could implicitly refer to the Nile. After all, all water in Egypt comes from the Nile.

The hieroglyph for the consonant *c* is an upholding arm is sometimes used as determinative for the word “give.” Pharaoh Akhenaten from the New Kingdom is often depicted receiving the life-giving rays of the Sun disk Aton, showing hands at the end of the rays, giving life through light. Does the hanging leg of the *ankh* symbol represent this reflection light of the rising sun on the Nile, which in the Early Dynastic Period represented the *ka* given to the Nile by Horus as Horemakhet and in later times Ra in the personification of Ra-Horakhti (Ra-Horus-Akhet), the Horus-Ra in the horizon?

Three bound together

The stone vessel in Figure [1] displays a band at the point where the loop, the horizontal part, and the vertical leg intersect, joining the three parts together. In later depictions, this connecting part often features a binding knot. Was this being tied together meant to emphasize the unity of these three aspects,

indicating that they belong together? It is only through their combination that they become the life force. Since the vessel is likely used in some ritual, we can make a guess why this ritual was performed.

The stone vessel exhibits holes inside that connect the three parts. Is this designed for the pouring of a liquid into the vessel, ensuring that all parts receive the liquid? Why other should they make the effort to put holes inside? Alternatively, if different liquids are added to each part, are they mixed so that the resultant mixture gathers in the hanging leg portion? This mixture could then be poured onto or into an object to imbue it with the force of life.

If we go back to the etymology of *ankh* being a composition of three consonants *ḥnh* respectively pictured as and place it like the following:

This reads as if the newborn sun, being Horus on the horizon, is giving his *ka*, which is his life force, to the Nile. My proposed concept of the origin of the *ankh* sign as a compound symbol suggests that the active life force is only realized through the unity of these three fundamental aspects in the eyes of the Ancient Egyptians. This unification concept was known in Ancient Egypt as the *Akh*.

The Akh, being alive

The Ancient Egyptians believed that when someone died, a crucial element of the person left the body. A person, when alive, consisted of at least six distinctive elements according to them: the physical body, the *ka*, the *ba*, the *akh*, the name, and the shadow.³⁸ The *ka* was considered to be the life force of the person, needing food to exist. The *ba* was something that resembles what we call the personality, and it has a will of its own. The name was important because it gave identity to a person. The shadow provided protection, not strange since they lived in a desert environment with a lot of sunshine. Shadow protects from the heat of the sun. Now, the *akh* is a special one in this group. It is the element that

only comes into being when the *ka* and *ba* reunite and after this reunion the person lives again and forever.

And there is only one place where this *akh* can be created by this reunion of the *ka* and *ba*, which is in the eastern horizon. The horizon, as we saw, is named Akhet and means “Becoming an *akh*” or “place of becoming.” This Akhet is the place where the *ka* and *ba* should already be united so the deceased person will live again. The moment the rising sun just becomes visible at the eastern horizon is actually the moment that Horus, in the identification of the sun god, is now alive again, and his shining light is spread across the country. Death and chaos are defeated, and a new fruitful day can start. This moment must have been a joyful moment for the Ancient Egyptians, watching the rising red-colored sun in the morning coolness. Wouldn't it be nice to symbolize this beautiful moment? Maybe this moment is captured in the *ankh* sign; it shows exactly this moment that Horus is visible and because he is visible he is an *Akh*. As an *Akh* Horus now can give his life force through his shining, reflected on the Nile.

The motive

It may seem a far-fetched idea that the *ankh* symbol would originally represent the rising sun as Horemakhet, who sheds his life-giving rays on the Nile. However, recently I discovered I am not the first to suggest that the *ankh* symbol was associated with the rising sun on the horizon. Simon Cox and Susan Davies give a summary of the proposed origins of the *ankh* sign and among one of them “depicts the sun rising on the horizon, thus symbolising the themes of rebirth and renewal, central to Egyptian theology. The loop would be the sun itself, the horizontal crossbar the horizon, and the vertical the path of the rising sun.”³⁹

The sun cult linked to the king was already in process during king Djet's reign (Cervelló-Autuori, 2011). So, if the origin of the *ankh* symbol dates back to the period of the kings Djet and Den, a highly innovative era, such a complex symbol could have been composed relating the sun with the horizon. Within the religion of ancient Egypt, the rising sun on the eastern horizon played an important role already from the beginning. The earliest representation of the

horizon dates possibly from the Naqada II period, probably in a religious context.⁴⁰ Could it be that during the reign of king Den and his later successors, a proto-solar religion developed in which Horus became associated with the sun, a process that began to take firm root at the end the Third Dynasty?⁴¹ The second king of the Second Dynasty, Raneb, was the first to name himself “Ra is the lord” and associating himself with the sun and there are more strong indications of the upcoming sun cult.⁴² At the end of the Third Dynasty the king's name appeared in a cartouche, which is a sun symbol.⁴³ These are strong indications of the personification of the king with the sun. But why?

The political influence of the elite increased during the reigns of the kings Djet and Den, resulting in the decline of the status of the king. We can see this, for example, by the fact that seals of pottery in this period begin to bear names and titles of officials.⁴⁴ There is also an indication that the division of Egypt into nomes (districts) dates from this period.⁴⁵ Each nome was given its own local ruler, giving him and his family more influence. This power shift had enormous implications for the governance of the state, which was previously under the sole control of the king and his immediate family. A response had to be found to protect the king's position.

From the beginning of the dynasties, the king was associated with the sky god Horus, possibly as a star in the (night) sky. In the First Dynasty this Horus was more a fighter, and as king who had to rule Egypt, for he defeated the enemy.⁴⁶ This is his more violent aspect of restoring the order. But this Horus, depicted as a falcon, probably no longer made much of an impression. Society became more complex and mature, that is, more intelligent and demanding. The king had to reposition himself as the highest in the hierarchy and yet remain divine. It had to be a celestial body, because, after all, the most important gods reside in the heavens. Looking at the sky, the sun is indisputably the greatest and most powerful object. By identifying with the sun, his power would increase again to this highest position. However, a shift from a falcon (or star) directly to the sun was probably too abrupt. An updated ideology that integrates Horus with the sun has more ground for popular acceptance. The implication of this new ideology is that a logic behind this concept needed to be defined. It is the old concept of the more violent Horus king becoming now a more friendly life

giving king as the sun god. One of the signs that a pacification⁴⁷ was evolving can be seen in the burial practice. From the beginning of Egypt there is evidence that people, most likely king's staff, were buried alive after the king died.⁴⁸ At the end of the First Dynasty this practice began to diminish, probably because family of the king's staff who belonged to the elite started to complain. A solution to this violent aspect was required. However, the powerful aspect of Horus as the defeater of chaos and restorer of order was still needed. This break in religious tradition took at least place during the 2nd dynasty but could have started earlier⁴⁹. The new element of introducing the sun god was that of a kinder but still powerful god who gives life. And "the introduction of the solar cult as a national phenomenon and the solarization of the monarchy in Early Dynastic Egypt must be understood as the result of political action and decision" (Cervelló-Autuori, 2011). Another aspect is that it has always been a challenge for all kings during ancient Egypt's history to rule the "two lands" as one state. For this the unification of the sun and Horus was also a political move. The Horus religion originated in Upper Egypt, while the sun religion was located in Lower Egypt. By combining Horus with the sun god Ra, he confirmed and strengthened his position as king of both lands. Evidence for this can be seen in the king's title. Den was the first to bear the title of being king of both lands.⁵⁰

However, as we would expect the king would now be the sun god Ra it was not the case. He was identified as the son of Ra and not Ra himself. Why was this? Most likely because of the "democratization" of rulership of Egypt that was already raised at such a level that this absolute power was not accepted anymore to be under the control of one ruler. The elite and priests probably did not accept the king to become the most powerful god himself like he was before as Horus. But as a son of Ra he was still divine and powerful enough.

With the introduction of the *ankh* symbol, the concept of "life" was deliberately linked to the sun and made available only to the gods and the king to confirm his divine status. This divine and royal aspect of the rising sun, associated with the king, is something that played an important role in the further history of ancient Egypt. We can see this when in later times the moment of the rising sun at the same time as the rise of the star Sirius, representing the goddess Isis, became the most important moment for the (new) king. Not only did this moment

of heliacal rising announce the beginning of the Nile Flood, but it was also the moment of the coronation of a new king, who on that moment became the god Horus and took his Horus name.⁵¹ The introduction of the *ankh* symbol helped the king regain and maintain his divine status.

Symbols have proven to be very powerful for us humans, from ancient times to even our modern times. The fact that the *ankh* symbol is popular even today proves this. However, because it is still not known what the ankh sign originally represented, it remains somehow a mystery. This article has attempted to approach this mystery with an alternative view. Hopefully archaeological discoveries will reveal which of the proposed sources was the real one, or perhaps even a new source will be discovered that was not noticed before.

Epilogue

Referring to fertility after all?

During a study⁵² on the etymology of the word horizon I found that there could be a relation of this word with “life” in ancient Greek language. The word horizon in Greek contains “ζων” (zōn) and is from the verb “to live”. In the study I show that horizon in ancient Greek “ορίζων” (orizōn) could be a composition of the words “ορί” and “ζων” in the meaning respectively of “rise” and “life”. In this meaning it resembles the concept of the ancient Egyptian word for horizon (*akhet*) as the place of becoming alive or reborn. On the other hand, the ancient Greek words for girdle and belt “ζωνη”⁵³ contain “ζων” and because of this also related to life. This is not strange since the waist is the location of the reproductive organs. In this sense life and fertility are closely related. Interesting is that the ancient Greek word ζωστρα can mean “loincloth”. Fertile in ancient Greek is εὔφορος (éfforos) and has no link with ζων. If the ancient Greek adopted from the Egyptians the concept of life to be represented by a girdle symbol it makes the case stronger that the *ankh* sign originally represented the waistband or loincloth. Although there is no direct evidence of adoption of the ancient Egyptian

concepts of “life” (*ankh*) and “horizon” (*akhet*) into ancient Greek, the above mentioned study shows it is plausible.

Ankh sign and the Christian cross

There is still a debate about the origin of the Christian cross if it originates from the Egyptian *ankh* sign. What can be added to this is that in ancient Egyptian hieratic script the *ankh* sign is sometimes written as †⁵⁴, which shows a resemblance with the Christian cross. Among the first followers of Christianity are the Egyptian Copts. The Coptic language is closely related to the ancient Egyptian language and in this manner it could be that the hieratic written *ankh* was introduced into Christianity by the Copts. The Christian cross was introduced in the second century AD, the same time the Coptic church was upcoming.

On the closeness of names and the referring object

That the name of a subject should be closely related to what it represents was very important to the ancient Egyptians. However, it was not only for them as we can read in for instance in Plato’s *Cratylus* which discusses the correctness of names. In this dialogue Socrates talks with Hermogenes and Cratylus about how names should be correctly given. In Plato’s *Cratylus*⁵⁵ we read:

“Plato: Then, Hermogenes, the giving of names can hardly be, as you imagine, a trifling matter, or a task for trifling or casual persons: and Cratylus is right in saying that names belong to things by nature and that not every one is an artisan of names, but only he who keeps in view the name which belongs by nature to each particular thing and is able to embody its form in the letters and syllables” (trans. Fowler).

Especially the phrase “to embody its form in the letters and syllables” describes the essence I think. So still in Plato’s time we see that a name should represent

it's subject as closely as possible, which was the basis for naming for the ancient Egyptians already more than two thousand years earlier.

Bibliography

ALLEN, JAMES P. 2002, *Middle Egyptian. An Introduction to the Language and Culture of Hieroglyphs*, Cambridge University Press

CERVELLÓ-AUTUORI, JOSEP. 2011, *The Sun-Religion in the Thinite Age: Evidence and Political Significance*, In *Egypt at Its Origins 3: Proceedings of the Third International Conference 'Origin of the State: Predynastic and Early Dynastic Egypt'*, London 27th July-1st August 2008, edited by Peter Fiske and Renée Friedman, Leuven: Peeters, 1125–1150

CRISTOFARO, ILARIA. 2020, *When the Sun Meets Okeanos: The Glitter Path as an Eschatological Route, from the Late Bronze Age to Archaic Greece*. *Journal of Sky-scape Archaeology*, Volume 6 Nr.1, p30-52

References

¹ DIMITRI MEEKS, *Le Signe ÂNKH ses Origines et sa Signification*, 2019

JOHN BAINES, *Ankh sign, belt and penis sheath*, 1975;

MARIA CRAMER, *Das altÄgyptische lebenszeigen*, 1955 pages 2 and 4;

² JAMES P. ALLEN, *Middle Egyptian*, 2001 p.27;

Sir ALAN HENDERSON GARDINER, *Egyptian Grammar-being an introduction to the study of hieroglyphs*, 1957, p44

³ JAMES P. ALLEN, *Middle Egyptian*, 2001 p.441

⁴ JAMES P. ALLEN, *Middle Egyptian*, 2001 p.154

⁵ MET Museum: <https://www.metmuseum.org/art/collection/search/543866>

⁶ HENRY G. FISCHER, *Some emblematic uses of hieroglyphs with particular reference to an Archaic Ritual Vessel*, *Metropolitan Museum Journal*, Vol. 5 (1972), pp. 5-23.

⁷ Egyptian Museum of Cairo: object ID JE47176

-
- ⁸ Pennsylvania University Museum: <https://www.penn.museum/collections/object/327782>.
TOBY WILKINSON, *Early Dynastic Egypt*, 1999, p250-251
- ⁹ The Narmer Catalog. <https://www.narmer.org/inscription/0079>
- ¹⁰ PETER A. CLAYTON, *Chronicles of the Pharaohs*, 2001 p.22;
LISA K. SABBAHY, *Kingship, power, and Legitimacy in Ancient Egypt*, chapter 1
- ¹¹ TOBY WILKINSON, *Early Dynastic Egypt*, 2005 p63;
ERIK HORNUNG, *History of ancient Egypt*, 1999. Chapter 1;
FRANCESCO RAFFAELE, <http://www.francescoraffaele.com/egypt/hesyra/den.html>
LAUREL BESTOCK, *The Oxford History of Ancient Near East*, Volume I, Chapter “Early Dynastic Egypt”, 2020. P285.
- ¹² TOBY WILKINSON, *Early Dynastic Egypt*, 2005 p93;
FRANCESCO RAFFAELE, *Late predynastic and early dynastic Egypt* (<http://www.francescoraffaele.com/egypt/hesyra/den.html>);
DOMINIQUE PERRY, *History of Egypt podcast*, episode 2 (23rd min.);
MICHAEL RICE, *Egypt’s making*, 2003, p153 and 167
- ¹³ TOBY WILKINSON, *Early Dynastic Egypt*, 2005 p177;
DAVID IAN LIGHTBODY, *On the origins of the cartouche and encircling symbolism in Old Kingdom pyramids*, 2020. P.16;
FRANCESCO RAFFAELE, <http://www.francescoraffaele.com/egypt/hesyra/5den.htm>;
HENRY G. FISCHER, *Some emblematic uses of hieroglyphs with particular reference to an Archaic Ritual Vessel*, *Metropolitan Museum Journal*, Vol. 5 (1972), pp. 5-23.
- ¹⁴ LISA K. SABBAHY, *Kingship, power and the legitimacy in Ancient Egypt*, 2021, p18
- ¹⁵ FRANCESCO RAFFAELE, <http://www.francescoraffaele.com/egypt/hesyra/ninetersvi.jpg>
- ¹⁶ ROGER WOOD & M.S. DROWER, *Egypte in kleur*, 1964 p.58
- ¹⁷ MOSALAM SHALTOUT: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/267729530_Solar_Activity_The_Nile_Flooding_and_Ancient_Egyptian_Civilization_from_Prehistory_to_Greek-Roman_Era;
- MIROSLAV BARTA, *Analyzing collapse, the rise and fall of the Old Kingdom*, 2019, ch2
- ¹⁸ GUSTAVE JÉQUIER, *Les talismans [ânk] et [shen]*, 1911, part of *Bulletin BIFAO* p125
- ¹⁹ HENRY G. FISCHER, “An Eleventh Dynasty Couple Holding the Sign of Life”, *Zeitschrift für Ägyptische Sprache und Altertumskunde* 1973-jan vol. 99 iss. 2
- ²⁰ HERODOTUS, *Histories*, Book 2 part 5
- ²¹ ERIK HORNUNG, *Idea into image*, 1992, chapter 7 “The concept of MAAT”
- ²² FLINDERS PETRIE, *The religion of ancient Egypt*, 1906
- ²³ *Dictionary of ancient Egypt*, by British Museum, 2003, Maat;
TOBY WILKINSON, *The Egyptian World*, p254; *Early Dynastic Egypt*, p173.

-
- ²⁴ TOBY WILKINSON, *Early Dynastic Egypt*, 1999, p249;
CERNY JAROSLAV, *Ancient Egyptian Religion*, 1951, p30
- ²⁵ PAUL MOULIN, "Essai d'analyse des calendriers Egyptiens d'apres l'oeuvre de M. le Professeur Andre Pochan" 1978
- ²⁶ https://www.wikiwand.com/en/Mirage_of_astronomical_objects#/Mock_mirage_of_astronomical_objects
- ²⁷ Diodorus of Sicily, by C.H. Oldfather, 1933, Book I 50.3 (p177)
- ²⁸ KARL JANSEN-WINKELN gives a similar explanation for the *akhet* in "Horizont" und "Verklärtheit": Zur Bedeutung der Wurzel ʕḫ, by Karl Jansen-Winkel (source: *Studien zur Altägyptischen Kultur*, Bd. 23 (1996), pp. 201-215)
- ²⁹ JAMES P. ALLEN, *Middle Egyptian*, 2001 Essay 4.;
IAN SHAW and PAUL NICHOLSON, *Dictionary of ancient Egypt*, 2003, (Horus)
- ³⁰ TOBY WILKINSON, *The rise and fall of ancient Egypt*, 2010 p.227;
MORRIS L. BIERBIER, *Historical Dictionary of Ancient Egypt*, 2nd edition p.30
- ³¹ DAVID P. SILVERMAN, *Het geheime Egypte*, 1997. p119;
JAMES P. ALLEN, *Middle Egyptian*, 2001 Essay 4.
- ³² WERNER FORMAN and STEPHEN QUIRKE, *Hieroglyphs & the afterlife in ancient Egypt*, 1996. p7
- ³³ JAMES P. ALLEN, *Middle Egyptian*, 2002 p.448
- ³⁴ JOHN BAINES, *Ankh sign, belt and penis sheath*, 1975 p21
- ³⁵ WERNER FORMAN and STEPHEN QUIRKE, *Hieroglyphs & the Afterlife*, 1996. p24
- ³⁶ IAN SHAW and PAUL NICHOLSON, *Dictionary of ancient Egypt*, 2003, (ka);
TOBY WILKINSON, *The rise and fall of ancient Egypt*, 2010 p.108
- ³⁷ ILONA REGULSKI, *A paleographic study of early writing in Egypt*, 2010 (p60, p70);
HENRY G. FISCHER, *Some emblematic uses of hieroglyphs with particular reference to an Archaic Ritual Vessel*, *Metropolitan Museum Journal*, Vol. 5 (1972), pp. 5-23.
- ³⁸ IAN SHAW and PAUL NICHOLSON, *Dictionary of Ancient Egypt*, 2003 British Museum, see akh, ba, ka, shadow, name
- ³⁹ SIMON COX and SUSAN DAVIES, *An A to Z of ancient Egypt*. 2006 p.29
- ⁴⁰ REGULSKI ILONA, *A paleographic study of early writing in Egypt*, 2010 p56
- ⁴¹ LISA K. SHABBAHY, *Kingship, power and the legitimacy in Ancient Egypt*, 2021, p16
- ⁴² CHRISTINA E. KÖHLER, *The Oxford History of The Ancient Near East, Volume I. part: Prehistoric Egypt*, 2020, p297; KAHL JOACHIM, *Ra is my Lord*, 2007, p61
- ⁴³ TOBY WILKINSON, *Early Dynastic Egypt*, 2005, p171-178
- ⁴⁴ RONALD J. LEPROHON, *The Great Name*, 2013. p15/17
- ⁴⁵ LISA K. SHABBAHY, *Kingship, power and the legitimacy in Ancient Egypt*, 2021, p27
- ⁴⁶ TOBY WILKINSON, *Early Dynastic Egypt*, 2005 p172

-
- ⁴⁷ ERIK HORNUNG, *History of ancient Egypt*, 1999. Chapter 1
- ⁴⁸ TOBY WILKINSON, *Early Dynastic Egypt*, 2005 p229;
DOMINIC PERRY, *History of Egypt* podcast, episode 2 (38min.);
ANGELA M.J. TOOLEY, *Egyptian models and scenes*, 1995 p8;
PETER A. CLAYTON, *Chronicles of the Pharaohs*, 2001. P22-25;
NICOLA LANERI, *Performing death, social analyses of funerary traditions in the Ancient Near East and Mediteranean*, 2008, p17
- ⁴⁹ JOSEP CERVELLÓ-AUTUORI, “The Sun-Religion in the Thinite Age: Evidence and Political Significance.” In *Egypt at Its Origins 3: Proceedings of the Third International Conference ‘Origin of the State: Predynastic and Early Dynastic Egypt’*, London 27th July-1st August 2008, edited by Peter Fiske and Renée Friedman, 1125–1150. Leuven: Peeters, 2011.
- ⁵⁰ ERIK HORNUNG, *History of ancient Egypt*, 1999. Chapter 1
- ⁵¹ TOBY WILKINSON, *Early Dynastic Egypt*, 2005 p 179;
G.J. THIERRY, *De religieuze betekenis van het Aegyptische koningschap*, 1913
- ⁵² ENNO NEETESON, *Exploring the etymology of “Horizon” and its ancient Egyptian connection*, 2023
- ⁵³ PAUL BEEKES, *Etymological Dictionary of Greek*, 2010, Volume 2, p505
- ⁵⁴ WILLIAM CLAY POE, *The Writing of a Skillful Scribe, An introduction to hieratic Middle Egyptian through the text of The Shipwrecked Sailor*, 2010, p302
- ⁵⁵ HAROLD NORTH FOWLER, *Plato. Cratylus. Parmenides. Greater Hippias. Lesser Hippias*. Loeb Classical Library 167. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1926. 390D-E, p31